

Stochastic Modeling & Applications

EDITORS

Debasis Bhattacharya

Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan, India

Carlo Bianca

Laboratoire de Physique Statistique, Paris, France

muk

S*tochastic* **M***odeling*
&
A*pplications*

Editor In Chief

Debasis Bhattacharya

Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan, India

Carlo Bianca

Laboratoire de Physique Statistique, Paris, France

Indexing: *The journal is index in UGC, Researchgate, Worldcat*

Founder Editor

A.K.Basu

University of Calcutta, India

Editors

Prof . Debasis Bhattacharya

Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan,India

Carlo Bianca

Laboratoire de Physique Statistique, Paris, France

Yuri E. Gliklikh

Professor of Mathematics Faculty

Voronezh State University

Voronezh, Russia

Prof. Sugata Sen-Roy

University of Calcutta, Calcutta India

Managing Editor

Martin Bohner

Missouri University of Science and Technology

Rolla, Missouri

USA

Editorial Board

M. Ahsanullah

Rider University, USA

Elias Camouzis

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens,

Department of Economics,

Sofokleous 1, 10559, Athens, Greece

B. Chaouchi

Energy and Smart Systems Laboratory (LESI),

Khemis Miliana University, Algeria

C.C.Y. Dorea
University of Brasilia, Brazil

Khalil Ezzinbi
Cadi Ayyad University, Faculty of Sciences Semlalia,
Department of Mathematics
Morocco

Nour-Eddin EL FAOUZI
Head of Unit | Transport and Traffic Engineering Laboratory (LICIT)
Université de Lyon | IFSTTAR and ENTPE

Lidia Z. Filus
Professor and Chair of Mathematics
Mathematics Department
Northeastern Illinois University,
5500 North St. Louis Avenue, Chicago, IL 60625, USA

Jesus Enrique Garcia
University of Campinas
Brazil

Enrico Guastaldi
Head of Applied and Environmental Laboratory, CGT
Via Vetri Vecchi 34, 52027 - San Giovanni Valdarno - Arezzo – Italy

Shezhana Hristova
Plovdiv University
Department of Applied Mathematics and Modeling
Plovdiv,
BULGARIA

N. Mukhopadhyaya,
University of Connecticut, USA

Mikhail Moklyachuk
Department of Probability Theory, Statistics and Actuarial Mathematics,
Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv,
Volodymyrska st.64, Kyiv 01601, Ukraine

Donal O'Regan,
School of Mathematics, Statistics and Applied Mathematics,
National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland

J.S.Rao
University of California, Santa Barbara, USA

George G. Roussas
University of California ,Davis California,USA

Naseer Shahzad
Department of Mathematics
King Abdulaziz University
Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

V.A. Gonzalez-Lopez
University of Campinas
Brazil

Sencer Yeralan
University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida, USA.
Yasar University, Izmir, Turkey

Xiaowen Zhou
Department of Mathematics and Statistics
Concordia University
Canada

A.Ganesh
Asst.Professor, Department of Mathematics, RUSA Unit Project Coordinator, Govt. Arts and Science
College,
Hosur-635 109, Tamil Nadu, India

D. Jaya Shree
Department of Mathematics, Govt. Arts and Science College,
Hosur-635 109, Tamil Nadu, India

MuK Publications & Distributions

F-2562, Palam Vihar
Gurgaon-122017 (Haryana)
E-mail: mukpublications@gmail.com
<https://www.mukpublications.com>

Stochastic ***M***odeling & ***A***pplications

Special Issue

On

**Recent Research on Management, Applied Sciences and
Technology**

CONTENTS

Research Papers

- IMPACT OF ONLINE & DIGITAL EDUCATION ON TEACHING-LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS** 1 – 5
MR. SATYPRAKASH R. PANDEY
- LEGAL SAFEGAURDS AGAINST FEMALE FOETICIDE IN INDIA: A CRITIQUE** 6 – 11
MAHENDRA KUMAR SHARMA AND DR. VINOD KUMAR SAROJ
- ASSESSMENT OF NODAL PRICING IN RESTRUCTURED POWER SYSTEM USING AC-DC OPF-BASED METHODOLOGY** 12 - 16
PRAMOD GADGE AND PRAKASH BURADE
- AN ANALYSIS AND COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF REDUCED SWITCH COUNT MULTILEVEL INVERTER TOPOLOGIES** 17 – 23
PARUL OZA AND DR. SWETA SHAH
- GLOBAL SECURITY CONCERNS AND LIMITING ARMED DRONE PROLIFERATION** 24 – 33
SAIRA GORI, DR. ANJANI SINGH TOMAR AND SANNIDHI BUCH
- ASSESSMENT OF DEGRADATION AREA DUE TO MINING IN PART OF KARIMNAGAR AND ADILABAD USING HYPERSPECTRAL SATELLITE DATA** 34 – 46
NAGARAJU THUMMALA AND A. NARSING RAO
- DIJKSTRA’S ALGORITHM FOR PATHFINDING** 47 – 54
DR. P. SOLAIRANI, PRASANNAKUMAR K AND VIDHYASHANKAR M
- A SCHEME TO DEVELOP A SECURE HASH USING MATHEMATICAL TRANSFORMATIONS AND RAMANUJAN’S PARTITIONS** 55 – 61
HARSHA S, BHASKAR N, KHALID NAZIM S. A AND BALAJI S
- CHARACTERISTICS OF NANO IDEAL GENERALIZED CLOSED SET** 62 – 65
DR. S. PASUNKILIPANDIAN, G. BABY SUGANYA AND DR. M. KALAISELVI
- EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT FOR PREDICTION ASSESSMENT IN MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS DISEASE PREDICTION SYSTEM USING DNA SEQUENCES AND STRUCTURE INFORMATION** 66 - 75
EDWARD DANIEL CHRISTOPHER B AND VICTOR S.P

SERVICE QUALITY AND MARKETING COMMUNICATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITY BRAND PERSONALITY, UNIVERSITY BRAND LOVE, STUDENT SATISFACTION AND UNIVERSITY IMAGE	76 – 90
<i>ABDUL RAHIM AHMED MUNSHI</i>	
FINELY TUNED MODEL FOR PROGNOSIS OF COVID_19 USING LSTM_FS	91 - 96
<i>DR. R. SENTHIL KUMAR, DR. S. PRAKASAM, DR. R.S. KAMALAKANNAN AND K. PRATHIPA</i>	
AI IN TALENT ACQUISITION ANDBENCHMARKING JOBS	97 – 101
<i>DR. R. MARY METILDA AND HURVIN. B</i>	
THE INFLUENCE OF SMES ADOPTING INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS ON IRAQ'S FINANCIAL REPORTS	102 – 108
<i>HUMAM ABDULATEEF SHOMAN, DR. SRI RAM PADYALA, DR. B. RAMESH AND KHEMRAJ ALIAS SANGAM SHET</i>	
CAUSES AND REMEDIES OF DELAY IN TRIAL OF CRIMINAL CASES: AN OVERVIEW	109 – 114
<i>PRADEEP KUMAR SAXENA AND DR. VINOD KUMAR SAROJ</i>	
$\bar{\theta}$-$\mathcal{J}$-CONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS WITH RESPECT TO AN IDEAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES	115 - 124
<i>M. VIJAYASANKARI AND G. RAMKUMAR</i>	
“ATMANIRBHAR BHARAT” REDEFINING FINANCIAL HEALTH AND GREENING POST COVID – 19	125 - 130
<i>DR. VIVEK PACHAURI, DR. NITIN KUMAR SAXENA AND DR. ANUSHA AGARWAL</i>	
A STUDY OF THE PROGRESS OF SELF-HELP GROUP-BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMME OF INDIA	131 - 134
<i>DR. A.C. PRAMILA</i>	
INTEGRATED PLITHOGENICTOPSIS PCM DECISION-MAKING MODEL	135 – 147
<i>S. SUDHA AND NIVETHA MARTIN</i>	
NEED FOR STAFF TRAINING AS A PART OF STRATEGIC COSTING IN TOURISM ORIENTED RESTAURANT INDUSTRY IN UTTARAKHAND: A REVIEW	148 – 154
<i>DR. DEEPAK SAHNI AND MS. ANISHA KHANDUJA</i>	
ANALYTICAL REVIEW ON DIFFERENT ALLOYS USED IN DEEP DRAWING PROCESS	155 – 162
<i>VIJAY BHAN DINKAR AND DR. DINESH KUMAR SONI</i>	
AI IN TALENT ACQUISITION ANDBENCHMARKING JOBS	163 – 167
<i>DR. R. MARY METILDA AND HURVIN B</i>	

PRIVACY PRESERVING OF STUDENT DATA FOR GRADE PREDICTION USING FROG LEAPING FEATURES	168 – 175
<i>JAYSHREE BOADDH AND DR. SHAILJA SHARMA</i>	
ROLE OF ELECTION MANIFESTO IN WINNING ELECTION: A STUDY OF 2018 ASSEMBLY ELECTION OF CHHATTISGARH	176 – 179
<i>RAHUL SINGH</i>	
INTELLIGENT TRAFFIC SIGNAL SIMULATION USING VEHICLE COUNT AND AVERAGE VEHICLE SPEED	180 - 188
<i>VIJAY D. CHAUDHARI AND DR. ANIL J. PATIL</i>	
INVESTIGATION ON GROWING TRENDS, CHALLENGES & APPLICATIONS IN IoT	189 - 200
<i>PARDEEP KUMAR AND DR. AMIT GUPTA</i>	
AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF STAKEHOLDER’S AWARENESS ON CORPORATE ANNUAL REPORT DISCLOSURE	201 – 207
<i>DR PREETINDER KAUR</i>	
A STUDY ON IMPACT OF RIGHT ISSUE ON CAPITAL MARKET: EVIDENCE FROM INDIA	208 – 213
<i>CA. JAI KOTECHEA AND DR. MADHULIKA GUPTA</i>	
SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS- A STUDY	214 - 219
<i>DR. S. MERCY SUHASINI AND SR. PROF. D. SREERAMULU</i>	
MODELING A FRAMEWORK FOR SMART AGRICULTURE USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS (IOT) SENSORS AND CLOUD-COMPUTING	220 – 225
<i>DR. S. KANNAN, DR. E. GAJENDRAN, DR. M. GOWRI, DR. J. VIJAY ANAND, DR. A. VIVEK YOGANAND, DR. S. LEONARD GIBSON MOSES, DR. R. DINESH KUMAR AND DR. G. CHINNADURAI</i>	
ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-LEARNING AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS OF DIET, AIZAWL	226 – 230
<i>C. LALSANGPUII, DR VANLALRUATFELA HLONDO AND LIANTLUANGPUII SAILO</i>	
GENERAL INTELLIGENCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AIZAWL DISTRICT IN RELATION TO THEIR ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE	231 – 234
<i>LALDUHZUALI ZADENG AND DR. DONNA LALNUNFELI</i>	
AN EFFECTIVE HEURISTIC FOR THE DISTANCE 2 MINIMUM EDGE CONNECTED DOMINATING SET IN A MOBILE AD HOC NETWORK	235 - 241
<i>REV. BR. SOOSAINATHAN, DR. P. SIVAGAMI AND DR. S. GOPI</i>	

ROLE OF DIGITALISED EDUCATION SECTOR IN MAKING INDIA A \$ 5 TRILLION ECONOMY	242 – 249
<i>DR. RAJANIKANT VERMA, DR. MANISHA VERMA AND MS. NISHA BAJAJ</i>	
GST COUNCIL MEETINGS IN INDIA: A CHRONOLOGICAL STUDY FROM 1st TO 48th COUNCIL MEETING	250 - 258
<i>MANVENDRA VIKRAM SINGH AND PROF. A.K. SINGH</i>	
FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF ATAL PENSION YOJANA	259 – 261
<i>AJAY CHAKRABORTY AND DR. S. RAJARAM</i>	
ANALYTICAL STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (ERM)	262 – 267
<i>MANISHA SHAH AND DR. SHEFALI TIWARI</i>	
MORE CHARACTERIZATIONS ON SOME PROPERTIES OF $\ddot{O}$-$\mathcal{J}$-CLOSED SETS WITH RESPECT TO AN IDEAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES	268 – 273
<i>T. SIVASUBRAMANIA RAJA, G. THANAVALLI, S.K. KANCHANA AND A. PANDI</i>	
LEADER'S PERSONALITY TYPE AND EMPLOYEES MOTIVATION IN PRIVATE BANKING SECTOR OF KOHIMA	274 – 279
<i>RAJESH TANTI AND DR. K SETHUPATHY</i>	
SOME APPLICATIONS OF $\ddot{O}$-$\mathcal{J}$-CLOSED SETS WITH RESPECT TO AN IDEAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES	280 – 286
<i>A. SARANYA, H. GOWRI, K. AMUTHA, O. RAVI AND A. PANDI</i>	
SOME KINDS OF $\ddot{O}$-$\mathcal{J}$-CONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS WITH RESPECT TO AN IDEAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES	287 – 296
<i>K. AMUTHA, O. RAVI AND A. PANDI</i>	
ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND FERTILITY RATE: A CASE STUDY OF THE EAST AFRICAN COMMUNITY	297 - 308
<i>RASHMI KAPOOR</i>	
ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOUR AND LITERATURE: A STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF AETONORMATIVE IMPACT IN ADOLESCENTS BASED ON <i>THE NAUGHTIEST GIRL IN THE SCHOOL</i>	309 - 312
<i>DEVIKA T.S AND DR SREENA K.</i>	
TORSIONAL IMPACT OF HOMOGENEOUS LAYER BONDED TO AN ELASTIC NON-HOMOGENEOUS HALF-SPACE	313 – 318
<i>NASIMA MUNSHI</i>	
ESTIMATION OF POPULATION MEAN USING AUXILIARY INFORMATION UNDER MEASUREMENT ERRORS	319 – 326
<i>MANISH KUMAR AND PEEYUSH MISRA</i>	

FALSE PROSECUTION, THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	327 - 333
<i>VIVEK WILSON</i>	
APPLICATION OF INTELLIGENCE IN SOLAR TRACKER FOR MAXIMUM POWER GENERATION	334 - 336
<i>PRASHANT BACHCHULAL CHAUDHARY AND DR DINESH KALA</i>	
A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ACCEPTANCE OF AUGMENTED AND VIRTUAL REALITY BY USER EXPERIENCE	337 – 342
<i>DR. SURENDRA TIWARI, DR. PUNEET KUMAR AND DR. KAVITA TIWARI</i>	
STRATEGIC TRAJECTORY DEFINED MOBILE SINK SCHEDULING PROTOCOL FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT CLUSTER BASED WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK	343 – 353
<i>R. GOPALAKRISHNAN AND DR. A. SENTHILKUMAR</i>	
CLOSE TO STAR ANALYTIC FUNCTIONS WITH ITS COEFFICIENT INEQUALITY FOR THE SHARP RESULT	354 – 362
<i>HONNEGOWDA C K AND GURMEET SINGH</i>	
A HASH-ABLE DATA-STORE PROCESSING FOR DOWNSTREAM ML FEEDBACK-LOOP ENGINE USED FOR FASTER INTRUSION DETECTION WITH LAMBDA PROCESSING AND KEY-VALUE STREAMING DATA	363 - 369
<i>MANJUNATH H AND DR S SARAVANA KUMAR</i>	
A GENERALISED REGRESSION BASED MODEL FOR OPTIMISING BUILDING PLANS FOR ENERGY, LIGHT AND VENTILATION	370 – 374
<i>HARSHA S, VAIBHAVI M. S, SINDHU K. V, AND SREELAKSHMI T. J</i>	
IDENTIFICATION OF EXOTIC PLANTS BY QUADRAT METHOD AND PLANT RESCUE CENTRE WITHIN GIRLS' COLLEGE CAMPUS, BERHAMPORE, MURSHIDABAD, WEST BENGAL	375 – 381
<i>ANKUSH PAL</i>	
SUSTAINING PERFORMANCE PROFILE OF SEIG USING OPTIMAL CAPACITANCE INTEGRATION UNDER UNCERTAINTY	382 – 395
<i>SYED FARAZ AHMED NAQVI, SUMAN DUTTA AND MOHD. ISHARAT KHAN</i>	
EMPOWERING WOMEN IN INDIA THROUGH SELF-HELP GROUPS: AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF IMPACT	396 - 402
<i>APARNA GHOSE AND DR. SANGRAM BHUSHAN</i>	
AN EFFICIENT NEW PROCEDURE FOR THE ONE-POT CONVERSION OF ALDEHYDES INTO CORRESPONDING AMIDES USING PEG-200 AS A GREEN SOLVENT	403 - 411
<i>NAVNATH D. GUNJAL, SUNIL S. BHAGAT AND SOMNATH S. GHOLAP</i>	
THE GREAT GODS OF SMALL THINGS: A STUDY OF UN-SUNG HINDU GODS AND GODDESSES	412 - 416
<i>CHITRA AGNIHOTRI AND DR. RANJANA DAS SARKHEL</i>	

CSR PRACTICES OF SELECT CEMENT COMPANIES - A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN KALYAN KARNATAKA REGION, KARNATAKA, INDIA	417 - 421
<i>PRAVEEN NAYAK AND DR. PREETI PATIL</i>	
DIAGNOSTIC INFERENTIAL METHODOLOGY FOR LINEAR AND NON-LINEAR REGRESSION MODELS	422 – 429
<i>C. DWARAKANATHA REDDY, K. NAGA VIHARI, K. MURALI, SREENUVASULU ARIGELA AND N. RAMACHANDRA</i>	
DIAGNOSTIC TEST PROCEDURE FOR MISSPECIFICATION OF THE STOCHASTIC LINEAR REGRESSION MODELS	430 – 434
<i>C. DWARAKANATHA REDDY, K. NAGA VIHARI, N. RAMACHANDRA, SREENUVASULU ARIGELA AND K. MURALI</i>	
NEW DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF EXPLANATORY VARIABLES OF LINEAR STOCHASTIC REGRESSION MODELS	435 - 440
<i>K. NAGA VIHARI, C. DWARAKANATHA REDDY, N. RAMACHANDRA AND K. MURALI</i>	

Received: 27th March 2022

Revised: 25th April 2022

Accepted: 29th May 2022

CSR PRACTICES OF SELECT CEMENT COMPANIES - A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN KALYAN KARNATAKA REGION, KARNATAKA, INDIA**PRAVEEN NAYAK AND DR. PREETI PATIL****ABSTRACT**

This article describes the CSR practices in Kalyan Karnataka Region of India post 2013 with special reference to Cement Industry. The 2013 amendment to the Companies Act made CSR mandatory for companies meeting certain criteria. Most Cement companies being large scale industries meet the criteria and hence spend at least 2% of their profit towards CSR.

Prior to 2013 CSR was optional and suggestive guidelines for CSR activities were in place. Post 2013 there were changes like areas for CSR activities being prescribed, limits on administrative expenditures under CSR, restriction on passing off employee welfare and marketing promotions as CSR, reporting CSR activities and expenditures properly, setting up CSR committee, having independent member in the committee and other such measures to ensure that CSR becomes effective in bringing about social transformation. Failure to spend CSR fund was made a criminal offense and later it was relaxed considering requests from companies to decriminalise not spending CSR budget, which now would be carried forward.

This study is based on interview with CSR officials of cement companies in the Kalyan Karnataka region and finds out how CSR has changed post 2013 and also compares how these companies implemented their CSR activities, as despite having several rules the Companies Act gives immense scope for companies to decide activities, identify beneficiaries and how they implement their CSR.

These comparisons bring out several areas of similarities and dissimilarities in the way the cement companies implement their CSR. While companies are in different stages of institutionalising CSR and having separate department for CSR, they have similar approach to identify CSR activities. They have some similar priority areas of CSR and identifying beneficiaries. At the same time there are differences in preferring project and programs, conducting public hearing, transparency and reporting methods. The study also identifies some best practices of these companies which can serve as benchmarks for other companies from cement and other industries to help in social transformation.

OUTLINE OF THE STUDY:

- 1.1 Introduction and background of the study
- 1.2 Need of the study
- 1.3 Objectives of the study
- 1.4 Scope of the Study
- 1.5 Limitations of the study
- 1.6 Research Methodology adopted
- 1.7 Data Analysis & Interpretation
- 1.8 Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

1.1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

The study has been carried out in the backdrop of India making CSR mandatory in 2013, to be implemented from 2014. Mandatory CSR is not universally applicable to all companies, but is applicable to companies which meet certain conditions of size, turnover and profitability. Also the fact that the purpose of making CSR mandatory was to ensure equitable distribution of growth and development to remote rural areas and also to make use of corporate expertise in bringing social transformation.

The Kalyan Karnataka region is blessed with natural resources, but the economic growth and development have been very slow. It has 8 major cement plants and 3 small size cement plants, apart from minor plants which are basically more of packaging units than manufacturers. Cement being a major industry with good turnover and profitability CSR would be applicable for most of these corporates. Hence it was decided to study the CSR activities of select cement companies in Kalyan Karnataka region.

Community is and has to be the primary beneficiary of the CSR activities. It is because of the community allowing the corporates to function as part of the society that corporates can use resources, establish business, grow and also contribute back to the society. The conclusions and recommendations made in this chapter when accepted with an open mind and applied in practice will certainly benefit the society by aiding the corporates and Government make CSR more effective and efficient.

1.2 NEED OF THE STUDY:

CSR was made mandatory for companies meeting certain criteria in 2013. Companies meeting the parameters were liable to spend 2% of their profits towards CSR activities. Prior to 2013 there were only guidelines and companies were not mandated so spend any specified amount, nor were there any restrictions on what could be construed as CSR activity. Post 2013 the areas of CSR spending were identified. The first decade of mandatory CSR is nearing its end and corporates by now would have acquired lot of experience and learnt a lot about how social development can be achieved through CSR activities.

Companies have a great deal of freedom in implementing CSR, but are restricted in terms of which activities they can take up. The reporting systems are uniform; hence there will be both similarity and uniqueness in the CSR policy, activities preferred, process and communication. There is a need for developing the CSR theory from how it is practically implemented and know how corporates view CSR. Study of these will help us better understand CSR concept.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- a. To understand the CSR policies and CSR priority areas,
- b. To understand the CSR process,
- c. To identify any best practices which deliver socio-economic and environment transforming results, and
- d. To find out whether the corporates were adopting a transparent approach towards their CSR budgets & practices and the methods adopted for communicating their CSR process with the public.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

Reponses are obtained from CSR officials of 3 cement companies. The other companies are left out for different reasons given below.

The CSR activities of other industries are not covered as the study is restricted only to the cement industry.

The study is restricted to Kalyan Karnataka region and the 3 cement plants covered are – 2 from Kalaburagi District and 1 from Vijayanagara District.

Three other CSR Officials have responded but requested the responses to be considered as informal and without permission to report. Three other company officials said their company has not spent much on CSR and hence they would abstain from responding.

The three official interviews are reproduced hereunder to understand the CSR practice of these companies.

The closed ended questionnaires responses are summarised into a short paragraph while the response to open ended interview schedule is reproduced briefly without changing the spirit and meaning of their responses.

1.5 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

It may be noted that while some responses are in detail, some have been answered very briefly some questions have not been replied. Some of the answers are opinions & experience of the employee, and hence may not necessarily be similar to the company's opinion.

1.6 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY ADOPTED:

The study relies on primary data and information gathered from the CSR officials of three cement companies. Some basic data – both Quantitative and Qualitative, are gathered using Questionnaires and data pertaining to the specific methods of CSR practices of the companies are collected using open ended Interview Schedule, with scope to add questions wherever required based on the flow of the interview.

Primary data from companies to understand the CSR process, the CSR activities selection process and CSR impact measurement and related matters was collected by in-depth interview using interview schedule.

The quantitative data is not analyzed separately as only 3 respondents are taken in the study and also because the purpose of collecting this qualitative data was to understand the implementation process in quantitative terms as well of particular cement company. Hence Quantitative Analysis is not taken up. Similarly Qualitative

Tools are also not applied. Only comparative analysis is done along with understanding the CSR policy, priorities, process and practices.

Data was collected from CSR officials using Questionnaire and Interview Schedule and the comparative analysis is carried out to know the similarities and differences in their practices.

Description of CSR practice and process of three cement companies by obtaining answers to open ended questions and presentation of information collected from the company officials using Interview schedule is done in condensed form without altering the spirit and meaning of their answers.

1.7 DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Data presentation is done in the narrative form to allow readers to easily compare the responses of the different respondent companies.

Three Cement Company's officials from Shree Cements, UltraTech Cement & JSW Cement (JSW Foundation) responded.

The summary of responses to the Questionnaires and Interview Schedule, company wise, is given below.

SUMMARY OF QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONSE AND INTERVIEW OF SHREE CEMENT LIMITED

Shree Cements has a dedicated CSR department and an environment department. The company annually published Corporate Sustainability Report which includes Corporate Social Responsibility Report. The mandatory aspects are reported. The company trains its employees about CSR as and when needed. Some employees regularly volunteer for CSR activities. The company has provided employees with written health and safety policy. Corporate governance and ethics compatible with the industry requirements is available in written form and has been followed. Workshops and training program for ethics and corporate governance at this plant are yet to be conducted. The company also has a comprehensive written environment protection policy. Corporate sustainability and CSR policy for suppliers and vendors is also laid down by the company. Only those who comply with these suppliers norms are considered for supply and to avail services. Company communicates about their CSR policy and activities to the public, mostly through their website, apart from mandatory disclosure to the Government. The company feels that the 2013 amendment making CSR mandatory was a very good move. The company had to make some changes to their CSR framework. The company is working in most of the suggested CSR areas, with focus on Education, Healthcare and Community Development. The company is aware of UNSD Goals and has incorporated few of them in their CSR activities. Efforts are also on to make employees more sensitive to reduce food waste. Company says it is procuring some supplies locally, and would certainly give priority to women and local entrepreneurs whenever possible. Company has also taken steps to increase using alternate sources of energy in some areas.

SUMMARY OF QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONSE AND INTERVIEW OF ULTRATECH LIMITED

UltraTech Cements has dedicated manpower and separate CSR department and an environment department. Among the various aspects of CSR the company gives highest importance to legal compliance, followed by attaching equal importance to UNSD Goals, Environment Protection, Relationship with Community and Dialogue with Stakeholders. CSR related policy towards employees and relationship with client and suppliers are not as important as the previously mentioned aspects. The company annually published Corporate Sustainability Report which includes Corporate Social Responsibility Report, apart from quarterly and monthly bulletins and newsletters. The reports are shared with Registrar of Companies, SEBI every year, shared with DIC whenever asked for, and bi-yearly with Pollution Control Department. Both the mandatory aspects and non-mandatory aspects are reported. The company informs its employees about CSR activities by sharing with them all CSR reports and allowing employee volunteerism. CSR policy and activities are informed to new employees during induction program. The company conducts both in plant and off plant CSR training whenever needed. CSR officials are made to attend training and conferences/workshop conducted by outsiders. The company has provided employees an opportunity to volunteer for CSR activities, but because of their work schedule, the opportunities are limited. The company has written health and safety policy of ISO standards. Regular training on health and safety are conducted. Corporate governance, ethics and anti-sexual harassment code are clearly laid down. To measure the outcomes of such programs employee survey is taken up. E-learning, on diverse topics, for employees is provided free. Company also celebrates Value Month to inculcate 5 core values central to the group. The company has a written environment protection policy covering energy consumption and conservation, alternate energy source usage, water usage, air emissions, waste management of plant and homes of employees, standard operating procedures (SOP's) for using restricted substances and chemicals and waste land usage. Bio Gas plants, using solar energy, 33% green cover, afforestation, plantation

programs are also covered in the policy. Policy for suppliers and vendors is also laid down by the company – suppliers have to be ISO 8001 certified, they must have ‘no child labour’, must be ‘equal opportunity and equal pay’ compliant, and also adhere to standard fair practices and environment friendly. The vendor’s declaration and third party audits are accepted and company does not inspect vendors. Company communicates about their CSR policy and activities to the public as it believes in keeping CSR information in the public domain. Company internally circulates quarterly magazine ‘Pratibimba’ which also carries CSR related information. All possible media are used to disseminate information to public. The company feels that the 2013 amendment making CSR mandatory was an excellent step and welcomes it. The company had to make some changes to their CSR framework. The company is working in most of the suggested CSR areas, with focus on 5 areas. The top 3 priority areas of the Malkhed plant are Education, Healthcare and Sustainable livelihood. Some CSR activities like funding institutions of national importance are done at Corporate Office level. The company is aware of UNSD Goals and has incorporated few of them in their CSR activities. Efforts are being made to make employees more sensitive to reduce food waste. The canteen committee and Guest House committee focus on improving quality of food, providing healthy food and reducing food wastage. Company says it is procuring some supplies locally, and would certainly give priority to women and local entrepreneurs whenever possible. Currently stitching of employees uniforms, procuring some food for canteen, face mask stitching etc are being done by local women entrepreneurs, most of who have been trained under CSR activities of the company. Many services are taken from local entrepreneurs. The company has also taken up desilting of ponds and wells near Malkhed, desilted 5 check-dams at Udagi village and constructed watershed projects at 4 villages. About 80-90 Mega Watts power from Solar Energy is being used in running the plant and in the residential area and utility centres of the plant.

SUMMARY OF QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONSE AND INTERVIEW OF JSW CEMENT – IMPLEMENTS CSR THROUGH JSW FOUNDATIONS

JSW Cement, an unlisted cement company, has a dedicated CSR department and an environment department. The CSR activities are implemented through JSW Foundations’ which acts as the common implementing front for all the Jindal group of companies. The company annually published Corporate Sustainability Report and Corporate Social Responsibility Report at following frequencies: quarterly for internal circulation, bi-annually for the Board of Directors and annually for the Business’ mandatory compliance. The mandatory aspects are reported to SEBI in a prescribed format are not public documents. The reports to Ministry of Corporate Affairs, CII and ASSOCHAM are submitted as and when needed as per the information needed/sought. Even the non-mandatory aspects are reported wherever needed in these reports. The company trains all its employees about CSR and provides them access to their CSR Compendium. **WASH** (Water and Sanitary Health) is a program involving employees to interact with public. About 40% to 50% employees volunteer for CSR activities. The company has provided employees with written **SHE** (safety, health & environment) policy. Corporate governance and ethics are covered by a dedicated separate committee. Workshops and training program are regularly conducted and even provided online. The company has written health & safety, ethics & corporate governance, CSR & environment protection policies. The company has conducted environment protection activities covering waste management, watershed management, dust separation, tree plantation, cleanliness drive, rainwater harvesting, bio-diversity park and has been adopting the **Miyawaki** method of creating dense forests. Corporate sustainability and CSR policy for suppliers and vendors is also laid down by the company. Compliance is checked using standard documentation and providing Vendor Code to those who comply with the set standards. Company communicates about their CSR policy and activities to the public, mostly through interaction with public, Gram Panchayat officials and mandatory disclosure to the Government. The company feels that the 2013 amendment making CSR mandatory was a very good move which has made CSR activities more systematic. The company had to make some changes to their CSR activities as they shifted focus from civil related projects to programs. The company is working in most of the suggested CSR areas, with focus on Healthcare, Education and Livelihood being top priorities. The company has robust CSR plans for the coming year and desires to cover improvement in CSR communication, improve their environmental impact, develop more socially responsible products, improve energy influence, reduce emissions & wastage along with increasing control over suppliers concerning human rights. The company supported war widows and their children as a one time activity. **ASPIRE** is a flagship sports promotion activity under CSR. The company has supported river cleaning and funded rehabilitation. The company also has a separate Rural Development Program. The company is aware of UNSD Goals and has incorporated few of them in their CSR activities. Efforts are also on to make employees more sensitive to reduce food waste through **Akshay Patra** program. Company says it is procuring some supplies locally from about 3500 self employed women and also helped 550 small scale entrepreneurs to link with markets. Company has also taken steps to increase using alternate sources

of energy in schools using wind and solar energy. Plans are in place to help the community utilities like colleges use solar or wind energy.

1.8 FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings:

- a. The CSR policies and CSR priority areas of select cement companies are similar to a great extent as they are bound by the legal provisions which prescribe many dimensions of CSR – from forming committee to fixing budget to activities considered as CSR to reporting. Hence there is lot of similarity in the policy and priority areas of the cement companies. There is similarity in policy and priority areas, but they are not the same.
- b. The CSR process of the select cement companies differ in some aspects from each other. There are unique methods adopted by these companies with respect to identification of activities and beneficiaries. There is also difference in preference between Projects and Programmes.
- c. The CSR activities of JSW Foundations dealing with Malnutrition is one of the most widely respected and appreciated activity which has been adopted by several companies across India and even beyond.

Similarly the way UltraTech involves its employees and community in CSR Activities implementation is a practice others can emulate.

The importance of contributing to the society through infrastructure creation – especially all weather roads, created in some places by Shree Cement is also worth adopting. Many villages and residents have benefitted in several ways after the roads were laid.

- d. Corporates are adopting a transparent approach towards their CSR practices & expenditures, but the methods adopted for communicating their CSR process with the public are not very effective and are not reaching the people beyond the immediate vicinity of the companies.

Conclusion

The Cement Companies have adopted CSR and internalized the process into their routine. There are similarities on account of the legal provisions and differences on account of freedom given by the law in the way process is implemented and activities are carried out. Transparency with regard to budget and expenditures and communication with society needs to be improved.

Recommendations

A few recommendations are:

1. Work with other corporates to pool resources to create financially viable and long term sustainable activities.
2. Have regular interactions among CSR officials of the various industries in the region so that everybody can share and learn from others experiences.
3. Work together to share best practices and also to improve efficiency.
4. Adopt a transparent approach to share the financial aspects of the CSR activities with the community.
5. Provide easy access to CSR information to the public through websites
6. Share CSR Activities information to public through dealers and channel partners.

REFERENCES:

1. www.mca.gov.in
2. www.ultratehcement.com
3. www.shreecement.com
4. www.jsw.in
5. www.csr.gov.in
6. Companies Act 2013

AUTHOR DETAILS:

PRAVEEN NAYAK¹ AND DR. PREETI PATIL²

¹Principal, Vivekanand Institute of Management, Kalaburagi, Karnataka

²Assistant Professor, VTU Centre for PG Studies, Mysuru, Karnataka